

Governing Urban Diversity:

Creating Social Cohesion, Social Mobility and Economic Performance in Today's Hyper-diversified Cities

Cross-evaluation report: policy and governance implications of the DIVERCITIES research on governing urban diversity

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The views expressed in this report are the sole responsibility of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of European Commission.

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1. Introduction: goals and methods

The first aim of WP8 on cross-evaluation is to identify what policy-makers and civil society representatives active on different levels (Europe, national, urban, neighbourhood) and working in often very different contexts can learn from the research results of the DIVERCITIES project on urban diversities. The second aim is to allow policy-makers and civil society representatives to update our discussions on the governance of urban diversity. The third aim is to create a forum for policy-makers and civil society representatives from various countries and cities to exchange and share information on governing urban diversity among each other. It is set up as a dialogue between DIVERCITIES scholars and policy-makers, civil society representatives and experts from all case study countries. The cross-evaluation has discussed the governance and policy implications of the research findings across all case studies of the DIVERCITIES project and the extent to which the DIVERCITIES research findings ‘resonate’ with the way policy-makers, experts and civil society representatives understand urban diversity and its governance.

Two elements are crucial for cross-evaluation. Firstly, the cross-evaluation aims to create the conditions for *mutual learning* between all those involved and treats all partners in the cross-evaluation exercise as equal. It is about bringing together different types of expertise and knowledge, most notably derived from academic research and practice. Secondly, cross-evaluation is *comparative* in nature. The aim is to compare and discuss findings from different neighbourhoods and cities in order to learn about positive ways of governing diversity in cities in Europe in general.

This report presents the main governance and policy implications of the large-scale DIVERCITIES research on governing diversity in 14 different cities in Europe and beyond. These governance and policy implications were identified, formulated and sharpened in different stages. The first stage consisted of a detailed reading of the policy briefs of the four DIVERCITIES research work packages (WP4, 5, 6 and 7) and the main conclusions from each work package as formulated by the WP leader. On the basis of this, a number of preliminary governance and policy implications for each of the WP themes were identified and written

down as statements. We deliberately chose to write them down as statements and not as questions to incite stronger responses from DIVERCITIES researchers and stakeholders.

In a second stage, we discussed these statements with the leaders of each of the four WPs. This allowed us to assess how robust the statements are when checked against the fourteen different cases. After these discussions, we refined, nuanced and re-organised the statements in three clusters, namely (1) social cohesion, neighbourhood attachment and everyday life in diverse neighbourhoods; (2) discourses, perceptions and approaches of diversity amongst policy-makers and civil society actors; and (3) social mobility, economic performance and entrepreneurship. These clusters do not follow the division of research activities in four WPs, but allowed us to group similar statements and minimise overlap between them. We then asked work package leaders to provide quotes and examples from the case study reports to illustrate the statements. The aim was to further check for the empirical robustness of the statements and use these quotes and examples to clarify the statements to stakeholders and feed the debate with them.

In a third stage, we organised a pilot stakeholder workshop in Toronto (we chose Toronto as it would be more difficult and expensive to involve Canadian stakeholders in a workshop in Europe.) We learnt from this pilot that statements are interpreted in very different ways by various stakeholders and that the national and urban context is an important source of the variation in interpretations. The quotes and examples provided to clarify the statements actually further complicated the interpretation of the statements and made us decide not to use them in the Antwerp workshop (but they are integrated in the discussion of the statements in this report). After the Toronto workshop we again revised the statements to make them as clear as possible, regardless of the specific national and urban contexts that people draw on to interpret them.

The fourth stage was the actual organisation of the stakeholder workshop in Antwerp (see appendix 1 for the program). This workshop brought together 70 civil society representatives, policymakers and academic experts from 13 European cities (and one from Toronto) to discuss how urban diversity can positively affect social cohesion, economic performance and the social mobility of individuals and groups (see appendix 2 for the list of

participants). During this workshop the DIVERCITIES team presented findings from four years of intensive research on the governing of urban diversity. During three small group sessions lasting for around two hours, we discussed these findings in relation to their own experience and expertise. Our focus lies on policy and governance implications of these findings for policymakers and civil society organisations working on various levels (European, national, regional, urban and neighbourhood).

To facilitate discussion, the group was divided in three smaller groups. The discussion was organised around the aforementioned statements and led by a senior researcher from the Antwerp team. As there were ten statements for each theme, we divided these ten statements over the three groups, so that each statement was discussed in depth in at least one of the sessions. The participants received the statements in advance and were asked to read the statements before coming to the workshop. All group sessions were audio-recorded and extensive notes were taken during the session by a junior researcher from the DIVERCITIES team.

In the fifth and final stage, the notes taken from each session were turned into reports, using the audio-recordings whenever necessary. On the basis of these group session reports, the senior researchers wrote this report. In the report, the statement is briefly contextualised in the academic literature and DIVERCITIES research findings. Then the main insights from the discussion with stakeholders are presented. These serve to provide further evidence for the statements, nuance and refine them with insights from various cities and merge statements on which the discussions overlapped. In one case, the statement was withdrawn, because some participants objected to the way in which the statement used ethnic categories to distinguish neighbourhood residents from each other.

In the remainder of this report, we present the main policy and governance implications of the DIVERCITIES project as statements, grouped around three themes.

2. Findings from the stakeholder workshop

2.1. Theme 1: Social cohesion, neighbourhood attachment and everyday life in diverse neighbourhoods

Statement #1: Residents of disadvantaged and diverse neighbourhoods chose to live there mainly for reasons of location and low housing prices rather than for cultural diversity. Although specific groups ('diversity seekers') may be attracted by diversity, policy-makers should not work with a general expectation that diversity is an important factor of attraction for these neighbourhoods.

In the literature on the creative city, the diversity of the population is identified and promoted as a factor that makes cities an attractive location for creative professionals to work and live. The role of diversity as a positive factor determining location choice also appears in the literature that explains gentrification on the basis of the lifestyle preferences of new urban middle classes, which are said to be more tolerant towards ethnic and cultural differences and often actively seek to live and spend time in places where these differences can be experienced. Our research does not find much evidence for this and shows that housing prices and location rather than cultural diversity are the main reasons why most people choose to live in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods.

For example, in the Paris case study, a French highly educated worker who recently settled in Goutte d'Or explains his housing choice as follows: "because it is the cheapest district. [...] Price and transportation. If you combine them, it was the 19th. [...] I was not specifically looking for a mixed neighbourhood". Similarly, in the Greek case study, a young Greek waitress who recently moved to Akadimia Platonos in eastern Athens, says: "I initially decided to live in Akadimia Platonos as it was close to my job. The area really suited me and it was cheap here". Still, a limited amount of interviewees also present themselves as diversity seekers. A middle-aged Moroccan woman who works as assistant manager in Paris tells us: "I come from Casablanca and Casablanca and Paris are similar. Lots of people

around, a big city. [...] It is the reason why I did not find it difficult to live in Paris. Because I am a 'popular' woman, I like people, [...] I like the mix!" (p.12).

During the discussion of this statement, various stakeholders raise important nuances and contextualize the statement. Firstly, several stakeholders argue that housing location choice is also determined by the presence of friends and family in the neighbourhood. Here habits come in as well, as some people live in a certain neighbourhood not because of any explicit, well-reasoned choice, but out of habit as they or their family and friends have been living there for a long time. Also, for members of ethnic minority groups, the presence of co-ethnics is often deliberately looked for, for reasons that are already described in the literature on ethnic enclaves. One reason that is highlighted as specifically relevant, especially when parts of society are hostile to migration, is the higher levels of physical, psychological and social security ethnic enclaves provide ethnic minorities with. Overall, the presence of social networks make inhabitants value living in deprived neighbourhood, despite often being labelled as less desirable locations to live by mainstream society.

Secondly, housing location is not always a matter of choice. In some cities, amongst others in London, housing prices are so high that inhabitants on low and moderate wages cannot afford to live in many of the cities' neighbourhoods and find themselves with virtually no other choice than deprived and diverse neighbourhoods. Also, in cities with a sizeable social housing sector, bureaucratic rules for social housing may strongly circumscribe people on low income's capability for choosing their housing location. Questions of affordability and access to housing are a key backdrop to debates of urban cultural diversity.

Thirdly, in terms of housing policies, there is an important difference between the city and neighbourhood level. Cities may have a housing policy geared at social mix, but this is not always directed at the neighbourhood level. Inhabitants may then be attracted to live in the city, among others for its diversity, but still live in less diverse parts of the city. This is often the case for middle and higher-class residents who may avoid diverse neighbourhoods, especially if they are also disadvantaged.

Fourthly, for many groups that are associated with the creative class profile such as artists, students and young creative professionals as well, housing prices and location rather than

diversity is what makes them choose to live in these neighbourhoods, although these groups are also often attracted by a certain bohemian lifestyle that is accommodated for in this neighbourhood and of which tolerance for and even engagement with ethnic diversity may be a significant part.

Fifthly, there are big differences in the extent to which cities foster the image of being a diverse city. In some cities, such as London and Zurich, a welcome culture towards migrants is promoted, which may stand in marked contrast with restrictive national migration policies (see e.g. Brexit). Cities that promote themselves as open, dynamic and multicultural living environments do not do so just for humanitarian reasons but to attract highly skilled and talented workers from all over the world.

Lastly, some residents of diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods perceive ethnic and cultural diversity in negative terms and they develop strategies to cope with this negative aspect of their housing location. This is reflected for example in the choice for a school for their children, where parents often try to avoid sending their children to schools with a high share of migrant children. This suggests moreover that whereas diversity may not be an important factor of attraction, it may be a factor that stops people from moving to diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods. It has to be noted moreover that school choice is as much – or even more – about socio-economic status than about ethnic background as middle class migrants often also send their children to schools with a lower percentage of migrant children.

Overall, we can conclude that policy-makers should not work with a general expectation that diversity is an important factor of attraction for these neighbourhoods. Disadvantaged and diverse neighbourhoods are mainly attractive as housing location because of their location and the presence of affordable housing.

Statement # 2: Policymakers need to publicly recognize the value of living in diversity and facilitate peaceful co-existence in disadvantaged and diverse neighbourhoods, for example through staff and volunteer training, assistance regarding financial and organisational planning for local organisations, providing networking possibilities and the establishment of community centers to support intercultural exchange.

Literature on diversity shows that some external intervention is needed in order to minimize negative effects and maximize the positive opportunities of neighbourhood diversity. In particular in an urban context, many challenges interfere – such as poverty, mobility, housing – and diversity in urban population intensifies the complexity of everyday life. The public discourse of policymakers – visible in political programs, official declarations, speeches and through policy measures – contains an ideological perception of the role diversity should play in cities. This public discourse explicitly either refers to diversity as an important asset in our current society, or as a negative phenomenon that has to be reduced. Even when public statements of policymakers do not contain any reference to the concept, it might reflect the lack of interest policymakers have for the topic of diversity. On the basis of our fieldwork, it is clear that local governments can make a difference by steering local dynamics linked to diversity. Stakeholders discussed in particular the conditions under which the promotion of diversity in an urban context might improve.

Overall, governments need to build more knowledge on diversity. More awareness and insight in diversity should support public actions towards the promotion of diversity. Policymakers are challenged by the different forms in which diversity presents itself. For example, an important distinction has to be made between diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods. Not all diverse neighbourhoods are disadvantaged and diversity should be promoted and managed everywhere, not just in disadvantaged neighbourhoods. Often diversity is linked to remote areas, while most of our policy suggestions for the promotion of diversity are indeed formulated for dense and disadvantaged urban neighbourhoods.

The need for more knowledge on diversity is also illustrated by the difference between neighbourhoods in the field of local economy. Public policies might support local economy initiatives, but this support is not always differentiated towards economically stronger and weaker neighbourhoods. In deprived neighbourhoods, it takes more time and staff to fulfill this task. One needs to invest more in building trust between the staff of public administration and local merchants. This is also the case for developing necessary informal networks. From Toronto over London, it is stressed that policymakers are in a difficult position to get in touch with diverse communities. Nor by personal experience, educational background nor class position, they have insights in how families in deprived

neighbourhoods try to manage their lives. It is key to help them analyse and understand the mechanisms that cause for example the high percentages of unemployment amongst certain categories. Without this thorough understanding every policy strategy will fail.

The discussion amongst stakeholders focuses extensively on recipes and tools to create an environment of trust. Promoting diversity first of all requires overcoming prejudices. Some neighbourhoods carry negative labels like: "If you want to be beaten up, go there". In rebuilding an environment of trust, one should avoid to use these stigmata and rather use a more positive framing. Also spatial interventions might contribute to create more trust among inhabitants of diverse neighbourhoods. Copenhagen, for example, develops varied built environments in neighbourhoods. Buildings should not occupy large parts of the neighbourhood and open spaces are created between the buildings, to which access is guaranteed for residents, for example for sports activities. The same goes for diversifying the functions of spaces that are provided in the neighbourhood, including notably planning free spaces that stimulate creativity, as is done for example in Leipzig. Also in Istanbul interviewees mention the added value of green spaces and mediating social relations through adequate infrastructure. Although interaction with strangers may be rare in public spaces, being there implies at least that people recognize and get accustomed to each other.

Participants have observed less public investments in poorer neighbourhoods, but feel that cities need to treat neighbourhoods equally in order to provide equal services in neighbourhoods. Indeed, when basic social infrastructure is present in every neighbourhood, living in harmony becomes easier. People meet each other in schools and on the local labour market and when equal access is guaranteed intercultural exchanges come more automatically.

By way of conclusion, policy-makers have an important role to play in promoting the value of living with diversity and supporting peaceful co-existence. This requires in-depth knowledge on neighbourhood diversity and social and spatial interventions to create trust in diverse neighbourhoods. More than focusing on the role of local civil society, participants stress the importance of public investment in disadvantaged neighbourhoods, since equal access to public services is considered to be a condition sine qua non for social cohesion. An overall

consensus exists that diversity policy should not lead us to withdraw our attention from these kinds of structural social issues.

Statement #3: Many diverse neighbourhoods have a negative reputation. Negative images of these neighbourhoods are mostly spread by outsiders and often do not match the experiences of the residents of these neighbourhoods themselves. Policymakers and civil society organisations can work with the more positive feelings of neighbours to counter externally imposed negative images of the neighbourhoods, for example by training and supporting residents to speak for their neighbourhood in the mass media.

The territorial stigma attached to disadvantaged and diverse neighbourhoods are a well-documented phenomenon in the literature on neighbourhood effects. Territorial stigma has an impact on the life chances of the inhabitants of a neighbourhood, regardless of their individual characteristics such as level of educational qualification. Territorial stigma may also fracture the social cohesion of a neighbourhood as inhabitants try to pass on the stigma on the neighbourhood to one part of it or of its population. Territorial stigma undermine the capacity of the neighbourhood population to talk for itself, as it sees this symbolic power taken away by external actors labelling the neighbourhood and its population in negative ways. None of the participants in the discussion disputes the existence of negative neighbourhood reputations and their negative impact on social cohesion and life chances for its residents. Opinions diverged, however, on the possibilities to counter territorial stigma. Among those who are skeptical the role of the media in producing and circulating negative images of neighbourhoods and its populations is highlighted. The media are said to thrive on bad news such as stories reporting on crime and danger, dirtiness and waste, drugs, poverty and most recently religious radicalism. Given the power of the media and the difficulties of getting them to pick up positive stories, these participants believe it is very difficult to go against the circulation of negative images in the media. For example, one participant recalls how a nice photograph of neighbourhood residents made during a positive neighbourhood project with artists was used to illustrate a newspaper article on anti-social behaviour in the neighbourhood. Another participants recalls how distrust in the mass media and the fear of misrepresentation in stigmatised neighbourhoods was so big that television makers who aimed to make a documentary on the positive dynamics of the neighbourhood found it

impossible to get access to the local community and find residents to collaborate with. They had to invest heavily in networking through intermediaries to establish collaboration.

Still, many participants feel that there are effective ways of countering territorial stigma. Strategies to undermine the negative reputation of neighbourhoods often involve people with expertise in symbolic representations such as artists, designers, architects or local politicians and celebrities. Other projects involve children and teenagers, which are given media training and television and radio equipment to generate and broadcast their own stories on the neighbourhood. Some participants doubt whether giving media training to neighbourhood residents is necessary or effective and focus on media access instead. They argue that residents are capable of making their own media stories, but often lack access to media platforms. Another strategy is to invite people with a lot of symbolic power to the neighbourhood, e.g. the prime minister or the mayor, to generate positive media coverage. One participant questions whether mass media such as magazines and television will still be important in the future and argues that the focus should lie on the decentralised – and hence more open – mode of operation of social media platforms.

Yet another strategy is to attract headquarters to the area (e.g. a training and start-up centre of a technology giant) and hence bring decision-making as well as symbolic power to the neighbourhood. A variety of this strategy is the building of iconic buildings and spaces, e.g. public libraries or the renewal of public space. The basic idea here is that public and private investments in the area create positive stories and raise press attention. Some participants claim that without investments of some kind, it is hard to change the image of the neighbourhood. These investments can be as small as setting up a small social garden in an empty space in the neighbourhood or do not even have to be iconic such as investments in social housing or other non-exclusive housing project. An essential ingredient of strategies to turn negative images of the neighbourhood around is 'local pride', as pride is what motivates residents to generate their own stories and go against mainstream representations of their neighbourhood.

A final remark is that the above strategies are all directed at the world outside the neighbourhood, often through the media. One participant notes that all this should first of all be done for the people living in the neighbourhood to give them a positive feeling about

themselves and the neighbourhood and let them share positive experiences with other residents.

Overall, we conclude that territorial stigma and the negative image of disadvantaged and diverse neighbourhoods are a well-recognized problem. The role of the media – mostly negative, but sometimes also positive – in generating and circulating particular images of the neighbourhood should not be underestimated. Although difficult to change, there are various ways in which negatives images can be countered, including supporting residents to create their own stories of the neighbourhood and give them access to media outlets (or help them to set up their own outlets), inviting people with symbolic power to the neighbourhood and investing in the physical infrastructure of the neighbourhood.

Statement #4: Perceptions of diversity of residents vary widely according to the place where one is confronted with diversity. Residents tend to be more sensitive to diversity in schools than to diversity in shops or restaurants and are more ambivalent about diversity in public spaces. This may have to do with the role of schools in the reproduction of people's position in society. Policy-makers and civil society representatives should provide more support to places and situations in which diversity is seen as threatening, particularly in schools.

How residents perceive their relations with diverse others is, to a good extent, shaped by their experiences in nearby public space (neighbourhood, shops, restaurants) as well as in local organisations such as schools, hospitals or voluntary associations. The social awareness of others begins with face-to-face behaviour in these local arenas and continues as people learn to account for and make adjustments (or not) to the presence and demands of diverse others. Within the group of local surroundings and organisations, schools are highly meaningful and often contested sites, mainly because they involve children and constitute the most important channel for social mobility and social reproduction. Diversity is seen as more threatening in schools because people fear it may affect the future life-chances of their children.

All participants in the discussion agree that residents' perceptions of diversity can vary significantly according to the place where one is confronted with diversity. Most participants

concur with the statement that residents tend to be more sensitive to diversity in schools than to diversity in shops or restaurants. For instance, one participant notes that school is “a site of contestation” because “it is close to people’s heart”. Other participants point out that in school parents are confronted in a direct way with diversity in their societies and thus become aware of the opportunities and risks this entails.

Various stakeholders, however, raise important nuances and contextualize the statement that schools are the most important site of contestation. Firstly, in some national contexts, the debate centres less on schools and more on the use of public space and the presence of ‘otherness’ in the neighbourhood (for instance, in the form of ‘migrant shops’). Secondly, the types of diversity that are considered to be problematic (or unproblematic) within schools differ according to national and local circumstances. For instance, the inflow of refugees and recent migrants into schools is a hot issue in Greece, while the debate in Warsaw is less about ethnicity and more about socio-economic differences in schools. In some countries the focus is on language differences and how this influences education in class, while in other countries this does not play a role. Thirdly, some participants point out that the perceptions of what is seen to be problematic (and unproblematic) in schools tend to differ between groups, for instance because in different cultures people have different ideas about the teacher and his or her position. Fourthly, perceptions can differ according to the types of school. In some cities, the debate focuses on primary schools, while in other countries secondary schools or higher education gets more attention

When discussing the possibilities to support diversity and counter segregation at schools, opinions of stakeholders also tend to diverge. One group of participants emphasizes that cultural and linguistic differences need to be taken seriously and should be addressed in the classroom. Taking into account, for instance, that cultures have different views on the position of the teacher, it can make sense to divide children based on their cultural and linguistic background, so they can feel comfortable in the classroom and develop self-confidence. Most participants, however, fear that such a strategy can lead to the creation of ‘parallel societies’ and emphasize the need to create a ‘social mix’ in schools and safeguard generalized quality standards in schools. This second strategy is often connected to the view that socio-economic differences are ultimately more important than ethno-cultural

differences. The latter are seen to be exaggerated, in particular by the media. Several participants point out that there is a difference between ‘perceptions’ and ‘facts’. While ethnicity and class are often used as synonyms – as when ‘black schools’ are considered to be ‘weak’ schools - empirical data show that most of the variety in school performance can be attributed to socio-economic variables.

Overall, we conclude that the need to provide more support to places in which diversity is seen as threatening, particularly in schools is broadly recognized. Although many types of diversity are considered to be unproblematic, some types of diversity – often linguistic or ethno-cultural diversity – can be seen as problematic and need to be addressed by school support strategies. There are different opinions, however, on how to counter problems resulting from diversity in schools. Some argue for mixed populations in schools while others see more room for group based approaches, so schools can accommodate their teaching approaches to specific cultural, linguistic or socio-economic groups.

Statement #5: The dense social networks that often develop amongst immigrants in diverse neighbourhoods can provide protection against the pressures and social exclusions from mainstream society as well as impose social control and push down expectations of its members. Policy-makers and civil society organisations should be aware of the temporary benefits the spatial concentration of ethnocultural minorities in certain neighbourhoods offers to newcomers, but should also attend to its negative effects when social integration in the broader society is not happening.

In the scholarly literature as well as the public debates on diversity in urban areas, there has been a lot of debate on the ‘ethnic enclave’, a term that is mostly used to refer to a neighbourhood with a high concentration of specific ethnocultural groups. As immigrants tend to cluster in close geographic spaces, they develop migrant networks—systems of interpersonal relations through which participants can exchange valuable resources and knowledge. Information exchanged may include knowledge of employment opportunities, affordable housing, or government assistance programs, and legal advice. Ethnic enclaves are seen to provide support to newcomers as they assist members in achieving economic and social mobility, for instance by creating an alternative labour market that is ethnic-specific and does not demand all the social and cultural skills of the host country. By

eliminating language and cultural barriers, enclave economies can thus speed up the incorporation of new immigrants into the local economy. Despite their immediate benefits, however, the long-term implications of participation in an ethnic enclave are a topic of debate. Enclave economies have been linked to a glass ceiling limiting immigrant growth and upward mobility. While participation in the enclave economy may assist in achieving upward mobility through increased availability of employment opportunities in the enclave labour market, it may also impede acquisition of host country skills that benefit the immigrant over the long run.

The different participants in the debate recognize that ethnic enclaves can have beneficial effects for individual migrants, but also emphasize the need to create connections between the enclaves and the broader society. Policy-makers should be careful not to create 'impermeable walls' (for transport, labour, etc.) around ethnic enclaves, but should instead build 'bridges to the world outside the enclave', in particular to the general, non-enclave labour market. Although the positive function of enclaves for newcomers are generally accepted, most stakeholders are therefore sceptical towards full-fledged policy support for ethnic enclaves, as this can lead to 'self-segregation', a breaking of the connections with broader society.

Several participants also raise important nuances to the idea of an ethnic enclave and its perceived benefits for integration of newcomers. Some argue that one should draw a distinction between the individual and group trajectory of integration. While enclaves may be beneficial for the first generation of immigrants, they can be a hindrance for second generations. Others point to the fact that integration is both socio-economic and cultural; while enclaves can help in integrating people in the labour market they can at the same time block cultural integration. In this sense, participants concurred with the double message of the statement, saying that "policymakers and civil society organisations should be aware of the temporary benefits the spatial concentration of ethno-cultural minorities in certain neighbourhoods offers to newcomers, but should also attend to its negative effects when social integration in the broader society is not happening."

Statement #6: In disadvantaged and diverse neighbourhoods, the arrival and presence of the new urban middle classes leads to mixed feelings amongst established residents.

Negative perceptions are related to the fear for rising housing prices, the loss of identity and the clash of lifestyles, while positive perceptions refer to an improving reputation of the neighbourhood. When approaching diversity, policy-makers should be aware that conflicts around living in diversity do not only revolve around ethnocultural distinctions, but also around socio-economic and associated cultural distinctions.

In the scholarly literature as well as the public debates, the focus of discussions on how to live together in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods lies on tensions between various ethnic and cultural groups in the neighbourhood, particularly from the point of view of the (earlier) ethnic majority or established group of residents as well as on the daily practices and lifestyle of poor residents. There is comparatively little attention for how the new urban middle classes are perceived by the other residents.

Our case study research shows that these perceptions are mixed. In several cities, residents report negative perceptions of gentrifying middle classes, referring most notably to the fear for rising housing prices, the overburdening of local services, the loss of identity and the clash of lifestyles. In some cities, these negative perceptions also extend to students, especially when they live in (and sometimes even buy) small flats, thus pushing up the prices for other residents. In some cities, no negative perceptions of gentrifiers came up. This may have to do with the share of social housing and the degree to which the housing market is regulated. If the access to housing for low-income groups is more protected, there is less concern about gentrification and the inflow of new urban middle classes.

Another concern is related to the clash of lifestyles. Members of the new urban middle class are often more vocal and speak out against certain practices and activities in deprived and diverse neighbourhoods (e.g. heavy traffic, noise, anti-social behaviour) that were tolerated by established residents. As they know the way to the municipal authorities and get easy access to functionaries and politicians, they often succeed in getting their way. Although certain residents value their presence as it may increase investments in the area and improve its reputation, others feel that new urban middle classes see themselves as morally superior and do not value existing shops and restaurants. The latter's fear is that gentrification is not signalling increased diversity, but middle class dominance. Participants to the debate also note that local residents often see new urban middle classes as symbols

of broader societal changes that are encroaching on their previously stable and secure neighbourhood life.

All this shows that policy-makers should not just focus on intercultural tensions or the behaviour of people in poverty, but take seriously the established resident's perceptions of the new urban middle classes. Gentrification is not univocally seen as a positive trend, invoking fears of higher housing prices, overcrowded services and the marginalisation of established lifestyles and activities.

Statement #7: Institutionalising diversity in public and private organisations by working with community representatives may work well as a transitional strategy, but should be avoided as a long term strategy since it tends to strengthen the social control of elites over all members of minority groups. Working with community representatives is less needed if minorities are fully socially integrated in society.

Aiming for diversity as a strength for neighbourhoods and organisations means proactive mediation in order to guarantee a representation of different categories of people. As literature shows, a common strategy to stimulate this representation is to proactively engage representatives of diverse communities in policymaking processes or neighbourhood strategies. These spokespersons or informal leaders are also considered as brokers. Especially local policymakers welcome these brokers in order to gather useful information to inform their policies and to contribute to realizing the goals of managing diversity. The benefits are formulated in terms of improved communication, better information and broadening networks. The risks of creating an elite and broadening the gap between them and the group they represent only become visible in second order.

The participants in the discussion illustrate both the risks and the advantages of working with community leaders. Everyone agrees that it is impossible for neighbourhood representatives to be representative for the whole community. In the case of Antwerp for example some shopkeepers started an association to promote their shopping street, but a second association was raised when some shopkeepers with a migrant background did not feel represented by the first one. Nevertheless, representatives have the power to open doors, represent people in their attempts to improve their living conditions and position in

society or support residents in their collaboration with other groups and/or with policymakers.

For local government, such representatives are very important to reach harder to reach constituencies and to mobilise them behind their policies and/or to steer their attitudes and behavior. In this view, representatives are vehicles for the execution of the policy goals of policymakers. Involvement of all stakeholders is key, but what about residents that show little interest in participation processes? In that case, participants stress that community leaders are even more important for governments, because no alternative exists.

Does local government have a responsibility towards these community leaders? In the discussion some concerns are mentioned about the weak socio-economic profile of many of these leaders. They sometimes live in precarious socio-economic circumstances, despite contributing to the wellbeing of their neighbours and neighbourhood. These voluntary actions earn more respect and government should help them get out of this precarious condition and support financially their efforts. No examples are known of compensations or financial support towards these volunteers.

Besides providing this material support, policymakers have the responsibility to act in a framework that sets goals on the long term. This means that the empowerment and strengthening communities and neighbourhoods as a whole should be their priority and aim. When the aim is to build resilience and make residents shape their own community, then devolution of power is needed. This implies giving money to the community and let them develop their own services. The risk that some have more power than others should be countered by supporting the empowerment of less powerful groups.

Overall, it is important to recognize that in many cities a distance is experienced between citizens and government: they have difficulties to understand and communicate with each other and collaboration does not occur spontaneously. That is why community representatives are needed to reduce the distance between residents and policymakers. In addition, the collaboration between all stakeholders is an ongoing and never-ending process. The discussion points to a specific threat: working with community representatives makes policymakers lazy. It is said that cities are complex and dynamic as well as communities are.

This means that periodically new 'kings and queens within the community' should be appointed to keep the system work and avoid the monopolization of the community's voice by always the same representative(s).

2.2. Theme 2: Perceptions and approaches of diversity by policymakers and civil society actors

Statement #1: Local initiatives that are concerned with urban diversity often work at the intersection of various policy domains, such as integration, culture, youth, sports and economic policies. Because local governments organise their contacts with other actors and their funding instruments mainly according to policy sectors, local initiatives often encounter difficulties when contacting local governments and applying for funding. Funding for and contacts with urban diversity initiatives should be organised across specific policy sectors.

Literature on policy management of wicked problems stresses the need for adaption of the more classical way of developing policies from a sectoral perspective. Because the definition of these issues is commonly multidimensional, several policy domains are involved in designing policy strategies to tackle these problems. Also more than one target group is at stake, especially when it concerns hyper-diverse neighbourhoods. The premise of this statement starts from the situation that many local initiatives depend on local public funding to develop their activities and/or on local regulations to get legal permissions. Therefore, local initiatives begin to contact local government without always knowing which department best serves the needs of their organisation. The call for a more coherent and integrated policy organisation is formulated in this context. Expectations towards adjustment of local policy organisation are less high if local initiatives do not need any funding.

Diversity is a reality that challenges any governmental organisation structure. Participants in the stakeholder workshop suggest that an ideal-typical policy organisation does not exist. The advantages of organizing diversity as a centralized policy domain in one government service is that it facilitates applying for funding. The rules for application and funding criteria are streamlined and simplified. The service is then visible and easy to manage. Competent experts serve individuals through an information desk (as is for example the case in Zurich). The disadvantages concern losing a tailor-made approach in local governmental services towards diverse communities and less support towards the field of local initiatives. Small

organisations prefer personal contact with civil servants, but because of digitalization of some of the tasks, this personal liaison officer is often not available anymore. Funding becomes less differentiated towards types of activities or organisations. Several examples were given of organisations that do not apply for funding anymore because of this loss of personal contacts.

An NGO representative explained: “On the ground it is more about the capacity of organisations to find ways that small organisations can talk to large ones; the government has lots of regulations which are often beyond small grassroots capacity; projects that got funded were often about ‘saris and samosas’, not those challenging existing power structures”. In Leipzig, local engagement officers exist that offer coaching and bridge the gap between organisations and local government. The answers to the question of coordination between policy domains also depend on the way competences are divided within countries. To what degree is local government competent in diversity matters? Finally, it is also crucial that the political level is part of the integrated approach. At the level of administration, coordination happens across policy sectors, but it is less effective if this is not happening at higher levels or among elected politicians. Most departments do not want others to intervene in their affairs. Without this political steering, it is hard for an integration department to organise ‘diversity’ across various departments.

Statement #2: Residents of disadvantaged and diverse neighbourhoods are not aware of most of the diversity policies and initiatives taken in their neighbourhood. Most of them are not active in bottom-up initiatives and there is a tendency to distrust politicians and public institutions. Policy-makers and civil society organisations should build trust and communicate more and in more diverse ways about what they are doing in the neighbourhood. They can also work with intermediaries, especially to reach the less educated and poorer people in the neighbourhood.

We observe a clear disconnection between large parts of the population of diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods and the urban public institutions and policy-makers that are officially governing these neighbourhoods. The increasingly diverse and rapidly changing population in these neighbourhoods challenges public institutions and policy-makers in establishing effective contact and communication and building solid relationships with the

diverse constituencies in the neighbourhood. This leads to a situation in which information about the policies and interventions of urban policymakers and public institutions does not reach significant part of the neighbourhood population. In Zurich for example, interviewees were sometimes aware of central state integration policies, but almost none of them referred to local policies. A female resident of German origin says: "I know that the city and the canton now and then launch an integration campaign. [...] But here in the neighbourhood? I even don't know what the district association does." (p.42)

The distance both residents and policymakers experience between their respective worlds often turns into mutual distrust, which further complicates the task for policymakers and public institutions to establish communication channels and platforms for dialogue with a neighbourhood's population. We observed often-intense sentiments of distrust and alienation towards policymakers in many cities. Residents in the neighbourhoods of Grünau and Leipzig Inner East explain: "Administration? Yes, in the past that was different. But, today, they only concentrate on the periods before an election. Then politicians come to our district and talk. But, besides this, we hardly have any contact to the municipality." "Do they recognise me? Do I feel recognised by them? No, I don't feel recognised and I don't expect someone to recognise me. Why should they?"

The need to establish trust with the neighbourhood population is a recurrent theme in the discussions about this statement. The role of informal relations is highlighted by several participants. This can be established through being regularly present in the neighbourhood, e.g. through participation in neighbourhood events or by going door-to-door to inform people or ask them about their concerns. Establishing trust may also require communication in a diversity of languages and forms. Another way of establishing trust and contact with the neighbourhood population, especially its low educated and poor sections, is working with (volunteer) gatekeepers, who are trusted by (groups of) residents and operate as intermediaries with public institutions and policy-makers. However, this strategy raises its own problems, as it is questionable whether gatekeepers represent the whole community and it papers over important differences within communities (see also theme 1, statement 7). Moreover, not all people are (and want to be) organised in communities and sometimes there even are no collective identities on the basis of which gatekeepers can be identified.

Finally, the gatekeeping role can put people in a position of dual, and at times conflicting, loyalties between the community they represent and the policymakers and institutions they have privileged contact with. They may also use the power they acquire through their mediating position to pursue personal or factional interests.

Yet another strategy, which addresses some of the concerns with volunteer gatekeepers above, is the integration of members of the various communities that are present in the neighbourhood in the city administration. This strategy takes quite some time, but it can reduce distrust as people now recognise their own group as part of the official institutions and may make these official institutions more sensitive to the diversity in neighbourhoods.

Some participants highlight how attempts to generate trust at the local level may be severely undermined by negative national political discourses on diversity. This creates distrust towards public institutions and policy-makers on the local level, which makes it more difficult to establish contact. Also, in neighbourhoods where a lot of segregation and distrust between residents exists, establishing trust between different groups in the neighbourhood may be a pre-condition for establishing trust in policy. Other difficulties in establishing contacts and dialogue with neighbourhood residents is about the management of expectations. Residents often expect that their ideas are turned into policy immediately or are only interested in their own immediate concerns and interests rather than in formulating and pursuing a broader neighbourhood interest and vision.

From a more critical point of view, some participants in the discussion question whether it is at all important that neighbourhood residents know about policies. The most important thing is that adequate policies are in place. Also, residents may not know which specific policies the city council is pursuing, but they do know the general attitude of the local government towards diversity, e.g. their preference for socially mixed neighbourhoods.

Overall, we can conclude that the establishment of trust with the various constituencies in the neighbourhood is a crucial factor to make effective communication and dialogue about policies for the neighbourhood possible. Creating relationships of trust is possible in a variety of ways, including the identification of gatekeepers and the integration of members of various communities in the city administration. Also, it seems less important that residents

know about specific policies, but are aware of the general attitude towards diversity. Negative attitudes towards diversity, also on other policy levels, have a negative impact on the capacity of policymakers to reach out to all sections of the neighbourhood population.

Statement #3: Local initiatives on urban diversity are more effective when they can focus on actual needs of diverse urban populations. They often experience tensions between their flexible approach and reliance on volunteers and the formal structures and legal status required to receive funding and the imposition by the government of strict policy priorities. Policy-makers should therefore be careful when imposing their policy priorities and leave sufficient space for local actors to respond to local needs.

Local initiatives on urban diversity are usually shaped throughout the interaction between different actors, such as city councils and administrations, NGO's, civil society, volunteers and the local population participating in these initiatives. All these actors have their own priorities and tend to perceive costs and benefits of local initiatives differently. In our research we have observed that this can create tensions between different approaches, for instance between the informal approach of NGO's mostly relying on volunteers and the more formal and legalistic approach of governmental actors. There can also be a mismatch between the approaches of governmental actors who often want local initiatives to contribute to their policy priorities while volunteers often approach projects as disconnected from political agendas.

In the discussion about this statement, stakeholders largely concur with the idea that different actors have their own agenda's and approach towards initiatives. There is no consensus however whether and under which conditions this is to be considered as problematic. Some participants see little tension and point out that "policy-makers are leaving enough room for NGOs", as policies and policy goals are usually written out in a sufficiently abstract and encompassing way. This enables NGO's to connect their own concerns with those of policymakers. Some participants also question the assumption, which is implicit in our statement, that NGO's are generally better connected with the local population and more informed about their needs than local governmental authorities: "It's really the question if the needs of these NGOs are the same as the needs of the non-organised population".

Some stakeholders share a critical stance towards government involvement, however, and argue that the autonomy of NGO's and civil society organisations should be better protected: "Politicians are grateful for all the volunteering, but the funds go primarily to the volunteer organisations who generally support the strategies of the city. Priority goes to organisations who push people back to the labour market". In some countries such as Hungary this even leads to the situation that existing NGO's, predominantly run by volunteers, are gradually displaced by new NGO's who are better connected and more supportive of local and/or national government: "we have new quasi-NGOs funded by the state and they take over activities. Government leads European funds to these new organisations instead of other civic organisations".

It is also pointed out that there is a trade-off between voluntarism and professionalism: "voluntarism and professionalism – both have pros and cons. Policy-makers should take this into account." One participant summarizes this as follows: "NGOs are very close to the people. But if grassroots organisations want to reach more people and grow, they need a legal status. So, that means more bureaucracy and restrictions. Funding means control here. Either you are a small grassroots organisation or you're a larger NGO under the control of the state." Most stakeholders perceive a tendency towards more professionalization and hence more control: "voluntary organisations cannot continue on this basis forever. They need some recognition and funds". This trend towards professionalization and a scaling-up of organisations is also connected to the way in which national and particularly European funding works. Financial and administrative requirements related to EU funds can be an obstacle for small organisations and a lot of grassroots organisations are too small to handle such projects. This can contribute to a 'frozen' situation where large and well-established organisations, which have developed expertise and experience in dealing with EU resources, enjoy a sort of incumbents' advantage, while access to EU funds proves to be extremely hard for smaller organisations.

While some stakeholders see more tensions between civil society and governmental actors, there is a broad agreement, however, on the need to structure the dialogue between civil society organisations, government and local populations: "It's crucial to have a transparent dialogue. City administration has to explain its goals." Because the public sector and civil

society have their own ways of operating, “we should not strive to unite them. The problem is always how to define common goals. And many things are done without public funds.” Some stakeholders point out that there are different instruments for local authorities to assemble information on the needs of the local population and their responses to local initiatives. One city official explains: “we implemented local participatory projects for those who do not actively participate. So, they can vote for projects and we get information about their needs. And we ask people to complain. So, we get information about their main problems. It works and they receive feedback. That’s very important”.

Overall we can conclude that it is important to guard the independence of local initiatives and to prevent an ‘osmosis’ of NGO’s and local governments. Policy-makers should be careful when imposing strict policy priorities and leave sufficient space for local actors to develop their own approach and respond to local needs. It is also advisable to better support smaller and volunteering NGO’s because they often lack the administrative expertise and experience in dealing with EU resources. At the same time, governmental actors can do more to assemble information on the specific needs of the local population and to make sure that local initiatives are in tune with this.

Statement #4: Local initiatives are more successful if they combine their local base and social networks with supra-local networks and resources. Public institutions, big civil society organisations and umbrella organisations have an important role to play in this. Financial support is crucially important, but non-material support, such as expertise, enabling legal frameworks, the provision of qualitative public space and logistical support, should not be underestimated.

This statement refers to the power of local initiatives and how this can be strengthened in order to give their activities better chances to contribute to the positive effects of diversity in an urban context. Power is needed to create opportunities for the citizens that are not able to deal with the negative side of diversity. This includes discrimination and social exclusion, weak social cohesion in the neighbourhood, difficulties in integration and participation. Restrictions are situated on both the individual and the collective level. In some cases the lack of power derives from low individual social, economic and/or cultural capital. In other cases it concerns the collective level, this is the power of the community or

the neighbourhood. To influence policies or societal dynamics in general, bottom up initiatives search for coalitions to enhance their power to act.

In most of the case studies, local volunteer-driven bottom-up initiatives were hardly able to survive on their own. Non-material and financial support is key to reach their aims. Networks are a kind of capital that strengthens the position of these initiatives. It concerns in particular relations with other organisations that can contribute to the realization of the former's goals, which seem particularly important for the improvement of the quality of services offered. For example, a social housing association in Copenhagen is convinced that health care is very important as an accessible service for their clientele and therefore builds its own health care center. This center does not only provide health care services for people in social housing, but also stimulates the relations between the center and other institutional health care actors.

In Warsaw, for example, NGOs cooperate closely on the support for children in diverse neighbourhoods by meeting frequently and sharing expertise. Local government supports this networking financially. While local NGOs actively contribute to this project, their umbrella organisations serve more as contact point for the government. Another example comes from Leipzig, where the organisation of an annual one-day festival celebrates diversity. Months of preparation help them build networks with different kind of organisations. An example of combining expertise is found in Zurich where the city has a migrant council, which took initiative to link 20 migrant entrepreneurs to young people by using the format of 'masters and apprentices'. This initiative was transferred successfully to the Educational Department. In yet another example, the Antwerp city council supported local ethnic self-organisations financially and with expertise in organising collaboration between citizens with a migrant background and their families in their country of origin. The idea to collaborate with institutional partners in the countries of origin came from the city administration.

Still, many governments experience thresholds when trying to build permanent relations and dialogue with local bottom-up initiatives. The reasons for this are numerous: contact persons of these initiatives disappear or change quite often, contact persons may be part of the umbrella organisation due to which local initiatives do not feel really represented and

contact other civil servants on their own initiative. To upscale the impact of local initiatives, the European Union might play an important role in promoting the topic of diversity and immigration. By providing European funding, items can be put higher on the national political agenda. It also allows local governments to get involved by applying for funding to support local diversity initiatives. In this context, participants argue that it is important for local governments to employ staff to organise funding applications. In Italy, for example, a decrease of local government staff had a direct negative impact on the amount of EU-funding collected for local initiatives.

Overall, local governments, the European institutions and umbrella organisations have an important role to play in empowering local bottom-up diversity initiatives, but networking between NGOs and other local actors may also contribute to this aim.

Statement #5: Local governments have a role to play in organising a platform for the exchange of experiences between local bottom-up initiatives around urban diversity, while local initiatives should invest more in their role as bridge-builders with public policymakers and service providers.

There is a lot of discussion on the respective roles of local governments and bottom-up neighbourhood initiatives in governing urban diversity. Bottom-up initiatives tend to criticise local governments for not being in touch with neighbourhood dynamics and developing ill-informed policies. Policy-makers from their side often perceive the local organisational tissue in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods as complex and fragmented and from time to time criticise local organisations for being too much focused on their particular interests and grass-roots and paying insufficient attention to the broader interests of the neighbourhood and city and the policy context. All this leads to calls upon the local government to set up platforms for exchange and coordination between local public and private organisations.

In Zurich, for example, the head of local division of an NGO in a deprived and diverse neighbourhood, calls for the creation of a central interface: “An intermediary is needed that would provide an overview of the immigration activities and the current requirements and would plan the needed activities of all public and private providers in the local integration

field. So far, there is no general systematic exchange of information between all relevant public and private actors in the field or a systematic approach towards the implementation of integration measures". In Budapest we find an example of such an interface, namely the 'Budapest Migration Roundtable'. The Roundtable is a citywide initiative launched by the Municipality of Budapest as a consultation platform in 2012 with a one-year duration. The project aimed at establishing a network with the participation of governmental and non-governmental actors working in the field of migration in Budapest and facilitating a citywide dialogue about migration and integration. The roundtable provided recommendations for citywide policies in three fields: social policy, culture and education. Some members of the project staff regret that the Roundtable came to an end as the subsidy period was over.

Most participants in the discussion agree with the distribution of roles as suggested in the statement, but draw attention to the asymmetric relationships between local governments and bottom-up organisations. 'It's all about power', claims one participant. In many cases, bottom-up initiatives depend on financial, logistic and other kinds of support from local government and may therefore lack the required autonomy to enter into dialogue with local government on equal terms. The importance of government support is stressed though by participants from countries in which civil society initiatives are increasingly asked to be self-supportive or receive fewer resources to carry out the same tasks.

Other participants argue that it should not just be about the exchange of experience but about actual participation in decision-making. Others are more sceptical about this and claim that politicians tend to decide everything on their own and bottom-up initiatives should keep their distance in order to avoid getting trapped in the bureaucratic and ideological logic of the government.

Overall, we can conclude that finding a good division of roles between local governments and bottom-up initiatives is important. Coordination seems a logical task for governments to assume, while bottom-up initiatives can build bridges with various sections of the local community. However, one should attend to the unequal relations of power between governments and bottom-up initiatives. While government support is often necessary for bottom-up initiatives to sustain themselves, it may also create a situation in which bottom-up initiatives can no longer talk on equal terms with government organisations.

Statement #6: National governments across Europe are adopting an increasingly hostile tone towards ethnic and cultural diversity. At the same time, many cities, sometimes supported by the European Union, are adopting more pragmatic and celebratory approaches, highlighting how diversity contributes to economic competitiveness and a renewed sense of social cohesion. How well are cities positioned to be the drivers of a new culture of diversity recognition in Europe? Which role should national states play in governing diversity?

Against the background of the refugee crisis and a larger backlash against multiculturalism, national governments across Europe have increasingly emphasized the negative aspects of ethnic and cultural diversity. At the same time many cities, which are confronted with increased cultural, linguistic, and religious diversity on a daily basis, have taken a more pragmatic and celebratory approach, highlighting how diversity contributes to economic competitiveness and a renewed sense of social cohesion.

In the discussion on the statement, some stakeholders start off by nuancing the idea that governments are adopting an increasingly hostile tone towards diversity. They argue that the hostility is directed not to diversity as such but rather towards immigration. Other stakeholders highlight that the hostile tone reflects a broader tendency, namely that national governments treat cultural diversity as disconnected from socio-economic diversity and economic deprivation, which can lead to the scapegoating of cultural minorities.

When discussing the different approaches and roles of cities and national states in the governance of diversity, most stakeholders are hesitant to make general statements, but rather stress the variety between different cities and between different national contexts. Several participants emphasize that “the role of the city depends on the position of the cities”. This not only includes their financial strength, administrative and legal responsibilities, but also “the political positions of the city council”. Another participant highlights that there are crucial differences between big cities and smaller cities, not only in terms of existing cultural, linguistic and socio-economic diversity, but also in terms of the approach and value placed on diversity, with smaller cities usually taking a less celebratory stance. Furthermore, the relations between cities and national states differ from country to country and are not always stable. A stakeholder mentions that there are national states

that try to curb the influence of national capitals, while others are trying to increase their influence.

In the further reflection on the role of cities and national states in the governance of diversity, participants emphasize that both policy levels have specific strengths and weaknesses. One of the main strengths of national governments in the governance of diversity, one stakeholder argues, is that they can provide systematic regulatory frameworks, as well as data, research and analysis on immigration and diversity issues. "It's important to measure and monitor the developments". The strengths of cities however, has more to do with their 'local knowledge' and their ability to adapt to changing circumstances. When reflecting on the governance architecture of diversity policies, these scale differences have to be taken into account. Ideally, such a reflection also takes into consideration the role of the EU, which can provide support through funding and networking. One participant mentions, for instance, the network of 'European cities against racism', which provides cities with policy knowledge and networking capacity.

Overall, we can conclude that the different approaches and roles of cities and national states in the governance of diversity, cannot easily be captured by generalized statements, but requires careful consideration of the national and local context as well as some reflection on the possibilities of multi-scalar governance.

Statement #7: Local initiatives around urban diversity tend to make use of the positive potential of diverse urban populations, focusing on intercultural dialogue, encounter and promoting an inclusive urban culture, while top-down policy programs tend to stress cultural integration and assimilation. Although both approaches of diversity can contradict each other, policy-makers can learn about the positive potential of diversity from the more inclusive and pluralist approaches in bottom-up initiatives, while bottom-up initiatives may learn from top-down policies about the conditions that are required to make living in diversity possible.

This statement is rooted in research findings on diversity policies in cities that highlight the differences in discourses and perspectives on approaches, and the success and fail factors

that exist between policymakers and private local initiatives. Although these differences are not always fixed, in many cases disagreements and discussions revolve around this divide.

During the discussion of this statement, many stakeholders recognize the evolution of political views towards more assimilationist policies and moving away from so-called 'integration policies'. The latter implies more efforts for mutual understanding and respect for differences in norms and values. But how does this encounter of different views manifests itself?

Most of the participants agree that local initiatives do have some power to resist the assimilation policies that (national) governments impose and often use this power. They should be stimulated to use this power and further develop their bottom-up initiatives. Representatives of local initiatives also stress that they are aware of the conditions that make living in diversity possible and do not always need collaboration with policy-makers in this regard. Still, in many cases government has the key to decide whether or not they want to collaborate with these initiatives. That makes local initiatives dependent on them and restricts their abilities to act in any direction they like. Some cases illustrate that local initiatives are forced to rephrase their activities in order to receive public funding for projects on diversity. They have to rephrase or hide their objectives to support specific ethnic groups because of the national assimilation paradigm (e.g. in Paris).

In this context, it is important to mention that governments learn and act relatively slow. As participants from London and Athens say: "Governments react in delay. It is an old system where you need to be patient. It is therefore important to be flexible and to lobby". Also, one election is enough to change the whole situation, as a supportive government may be replaced by one more hostile to bottom-up integration initiatives or vice versa, which makes the work of bottom-up initiatives more difficult or sometimes completely impossible to sustain over time.

Statement #8: The diversity in particular countries and cities can be the result of a colonial past, guest worker schemes, family reunification, asylum seeker provisions, etc. The position and trajectory of migrants in the host country therefore varies widely. Policy-makers need to adapt their expectations of migrants and migration to the on-the-ground

realities of diversity and develop context-sensitive rather than ‘one size fits all’ policies and strategies. They also need to be careful when transferring ‘best practices’ from one city to another.

Multicultural policies and strategies to develop group-differentiated rights for ethnic-cultural minorities have been blamed for downplaying the internal heterogeneity of ethnic-cultural groups. Recent discussions on ‘hyper-diversity’ and ‘superdiversity’ have drawn attention to the diversity within the diversity, both in terms of the intersection of ethnic and cultural forms of diversity with other axes of social differentiation as well as in terms of the very different trajectories migrants – even from the same country of origin – have traversed.

Indeed, past and current migration processes shape cities and their populations in entirely different ways. The colonial past and the concentration of world economic functions made London and Paris into diverse cities. The imperial past shaped diversity in Tallinn and Istanbul, the latter also receiving massive internal rural-urban migration waves more recently. Zurich has been diversified in the postwar decades through successive waves of economic migration, while cities like Athens and Milan have only seen diversification more recently, largely through migration that followed the fall of communist regimes in Eastern Europe. Other cities experience more modest degrees of diversity which may be associated with the long-term presence of minorities, like the Roma in Budapest, or with internal processes of socio-economic transformation, like those that shrunk the population of Leipzig after the regime change and increased the share of the elderly in the city. The very different origins of diversity within a particular society matters greatly for the ways in which diverse populations can be incorporated into society, given that it is associated with different levels of qualification, legal statutes, relation with the country of origin, degree of shared history, etc. All this pleads for context-sensitive policies and strategies to govern urban diversity.

Awareness of diversity within diversity leads some participants to call for inclusive forms of urban citizenship rather than ethnic forms of organisation and mobilisation or cultural group differentiated rights. Urban citizenship is grounded in a shared responsibility for the city and neighbourhoods one inhabits, regardless of one’s ethnic and cultural background, and focuses on equal rights for each citizen. According to some, the latter implies a civil rights movement to fight for equal rights for all citizens, notably people with a migration

background because they are regularly confronted with discrimination and racism and the violation of their basic human rights. In this context, other participants argue that we should stop labelling only members of minorities in ethnic terms while the (initial) majority is not seen to have any ethnicity.

By way of conclusion, awareness of diversity within the diversity should be promoted with policymakers and civil society organisations. This awareness should lead to context-sensitive strategies to govern urban diversity and a focus on shared and inclusive urban citizenship is that which keeps inhabitants of all different ethnic backgrounds together.

Statement #9: Policy concerns are increasingly focused on individual aspirations and responsibilities and downplay structural explanations for social and economic inequalities. This creates a bias towards the ‘successful’ aspects of diversity in cities, e.g. successful migrant entrepreneurs, while other parts of the urban diverse population are less valued by policy-makers. Policy-makers and civil society initiatives should value all sections of the diverse urban population and should give more attention to equality of outcomes rather than just equality of opportunities.

In the last decennium, many cities have emphasized the positive economic aspects of diversity in cities, such as the contribution that diversity can make to economic growth and innovation. Cities increasingly build on economic and management ideas about the relative competitive advantages of diversity, an idea that not only applies to businesses, but is also often extended to nations and other organisations. Our research shows that such an economic approach to diversity often leads to a focus on successful categories of the diverse population, such as migrant entrepreneurs, while other parts of the urban diverse population are less valued by policy-makers. A further consequence of this focus is that policies are mainly driven by a concern of promoting ‘equality of opportunities’ while policies striving for ‘equality of outcomes’ have been largely delegitimized.

The stakeholders participating in the discussion demonstrated an unusual degree of agreement with the statement. One participant observed that there is “increasing emphasis on competitiveness” and on successful stories. Cities, however, “should not only find positive examples of diversity, but also talk about equality and inequality of the people”.

Others added to this that “we’re creating future problems if we’re not focusing on structural explanations for the marginalization of migrant populations”. Most urban diversity policies are experienced as being one-sidedly focused on individual aspirations and responsibilities and as hesitant and even hostile towards actions focusing on the improvement of collective agency: “In our organisation, it is prohibited to concentrate on structural problems. It’s all about helping people on an individual level. The city administration tells us that we should not group people together and raise their voices, or otherwise they will cut our funds.”

The individualist bias of current policy discourse leads some participants to call for more group-targeted and outcome-oriented approaches: “all approaches are becoming mainstreamed at the moment. Specific approaches do not exist anymore. It’s the fear of alienation of people. And that certain groups are getting neglected. Equality of opportunities is important, but not enough. The outcomes should be in the focus”.

By way of conclusion we can thus concur with our statement that policy-makers and civil society initiatives should pay more attention to segments of the diverse urban population that are currently undervalued because they are economically less successful; such an approach can go hand in hand with an renewed policy emphasis on equality of outcomes rather than just equality of opportunities.

Statement #10: Policies and policy changes, e.g. budget cuts, are not diversity neutral and often have strong impacts on vulnerable populations with a migrant background. An awareness and recognition of diversity should inform all welfare and planning policies (e.g. through an ex ante ‘diversity test’ of new policy measures).

In democracies, policies reflect political choices legitimately made by elected politicians. Policies are therefore not neutral, but impact some social groups more than others. The question is raised whether policies that are disproportionately impacting on inhabitants with a migrant background – whether intended that way or not – are democratically legitimate or discriminatory. This question is all the more important given the vulnerable socio-economic position of many inhabitants with a migrant background. To address this issue, calls are made to take diversity more explicitly into account when formulating welfare and planning policies. This can be done in different ways, amongst others through an ex ante ‘diversity

test' of new policy measures or the integration of vulnerable populations in policy making processes.

For example, there have been efforts in some Eastern European cities to involve vulnerable populations, particularly the Roma, in policy making. In Budapest, based on the experiences of URBACT II/Roma-Net 'Integration of Roma population in Budapest' project, the Roundtable of Migration was set up. In London special guidance for diversity planning is a part of the city's strategic Plan. The Guidance explicitly aims to promote social inclusion and help eliminate discrimination by ensuring that the spatial needs of all London's communities are addressed. Local boroughs are required to identify the needs of the diverse groups in their area, address the spatial needs of these groups and ensure that they are not disadvantaged both through general policies for development and specific policies relating to the provision of social infrastructure.

This statement proves controversial with the participants in the discussion. Some participants argue that this involves 'ethnic profiling' of inhabitants and is therefore problematic on ethical grounds. They argue that using ethnic categories creates its own reality and can become self-fulfilling. It would be better to focus on socio-economic rather than ethnic categories. Moreover, even if a disproportionate impact on one or more ethnic groups is observed, it may probably stand the juridical test if there is no observable racist intention on the part of policymakers. Others argue that we need ethnic categories in order to make visible what is going wrong. If we do not have statistics on the level of poverty amongst certain ethnic groups, how do we know about this specific problem and which changes are needed to address it?

Overall, there is a lot of disagreement about whether and how diversity considerations should inform welfare and planning policies. Still, we would argue that if policies have a disproportionate impact on certain ethnic-cultural groups, it merits democratic debate, but this democratic debate has to be waged in terms that are sensitive to the approaches of diversity that are existing in different countries.

2.3. Theme 3: Social mobility, economic performance and entrepreneurship in diverse neighbourhoods

Statement #1: Whereas most creative enterprises and highly skilled entrepreneurs in diverse neighbourhoods perform well economically, many ‘non-innovative’ immigrant enterprises often generate just enough money to make ends meet. Still local policies often have a one-sided focus on the highly skilled, creative or innovative enterprises and can therefore become more effective by taking into account the full variety of entrepreneurship in diverse neighbourhoods.

After decades of economic suburbanisation and deindustrialisation, cities have been promoted in their new economic role as hubs for high tech and creative economies. Because of their density, proximity and heterogeneity urban places are considered platforms for innovation and entrepreneurship. This urban innovation discourse is highly influential in policymaking circles, leading to the establishment of creative zones and innovation districts. In Copenhagen, for example, the municipal council launched a strategy to support creative enterprises and enterprises with a social purpose. The area around Rentemestervej Street in Bispebjerg has been designated a ‘creative zone’ as part of a citywide municipal strategy aimed at preserving urban areas with a distinct physical character and with attractive conditions for start-up entrepreneurs. The area in Bispebjerg has been selected for its old factories and workshops, which offer low-rent facilities for businesses. In all creative zones, Copenhagen Municipality has set the maximum plot ratios at 60% to ensure that plots are unattractive for the construction of new buildings and to preserve the existing building stock and low rent levels. Another example is in Athens, where in the midst of the crisis, an initiative has been taken by the municipality to establish the ‘Pole for Innovation and Entrepreneurship INNOVATHENS’. This agency provides entrepreneurs with know-how and skills in product, services and process innovation.

Several participants shared the criticism that these targeted initiatives for creative and high tech entrepreneurs focus on only group of entrepreneurs and ignore another and perhaps bigger group of entrepreneurs – more often than not with a migrant background – that are not specifically innovative in what they do (grocery stores, call shops, night shops, low price cloth shops, bars, etc.). Many of these non-innovative businesses are struggling to survive, but nevertheless provide an income to vulnerable families and frequently have an important

social role in the neighbourhood. Yet, local governments seldom have policies to support these kind of non-innovative businesses. Quite to the contrary, some cities even have policies to discourage the establishment of these kinds of businesses (e.g. the tax on 'image lowering businesses' in Antwerp). As participants in the discussion observe, the differential treatment of businesses in neighbourhoods imply strong value judgments on the people involved in them and the products and services sold. Migrant entrepreneurs are said to be aware of these implied judgements.

Overall, it seems important that policymakers do treat all businesses and entrepreneurs as equally deserving of support and policy attention, perhaps with extra attention and support for those enterprises that are important sources of income for vulnerable families and/or have an important social role in the neighbourhood.

Statement #2: Although creative and high-tech enterprises receive substantial attention and support from local governments and often improve the image of deprived neighbourhoods and attract new customer groups, they are mostly not well connected to the diversity of the neighbourhood. Local governments should support the involvement of migrants in the local creative and high-tech economy, for example by supporting intermediaries and establishing platforms of exchange and dialogue. Local policies should also pay more attention to the impact of regeneration policies on small and migrant businesses and the vitality of street life and take measures to prevent displacement.

In the last decennium the literature on urban diversity and economic performance has emphasized the importance of creative and high-skilled entrepreneurs, who are believed to play an important role in the regeneration of deprived and diverse areas. According to the seminal ideas of Richard Florida, for instance, attracting the high-skilled knowledge workers of the 'creative class' would be crucial for the economic development of post-industrial cities. For this reason, many cities implemented policies promoting themselves as tolerant places open to diversity in order to attract high-skilled and creative entrepreneurs. From our research we have learned that such policies can improve the image of deprived neighbourhoods and make them more attractive for higher-income residents. A possible downside of this policy, however, is that higher-income residents and entrepreneurs are

mostly not well connected to the diversity of the neighbourhood. High-tech firms seldom employ residents from deprived neighbourhoods. Furthermore, most ethnic entrepreneurs work in low-end sectors like retail, pubs and restaurants, on which urban policies do not always spend the same amount of attention.

The inflow of creative entrepreneurs can also lead to gentrification, resulting in higher costs of housing and living and original residents and entrepreneurs being pushed out of the neighbourhood. This effect can be amplified by urban regeneration policies, which can generate displacement pressures on the small and migrant businesses in the area. Because of urban regeneration, the reputation of the London Hackney neighbourhood, for instance, was turned around, which led to a steep increase of the land value. This was good for the developers, yet also led to a rise of rental prices and hence prevented a lot of the original inhabitants to return to their neighbourhood. Neighbourhood transformation thus changes the local needs and the composition of local businesses. Often, no plan is available that anticipates and coordinates the economic needs and innovations that suits the new socio-economic profile of the neighbourhood after regeneration has occurred. Of course, social reality is not entirely predictable and planning has its limits. Still, participants agree on the need for more creativity and engagement to help new businesses (even the bigger ones) that create new activities and jobs and to protect small enterprises at the same time. Importantly, according to the research findings, urban renewal is not in all cities perceived to be a negative phenomenon. In cities like Tallinn and Warsaw, several positive opinions about urban renewal are registered, e.g. an improved image of the neighbourhood and increased local purchasing power.

When discussing the statement, most participants concurred with the diagnosis that creative enterprises do not necessarily contribute to vulnerable neighbourhoods. They were however, rather sceptical of the policy recommendation that local governments should support the involvement of migrants in the local creative and high-tech economy, for example by supporting intermediaries. Several respondents noted that “we should not force firms to involve people from the neighbourhood”. There can be no obligation to actively involve or hire local people, “because this would push these enterprises out of these neighbourhoods; imposed obligations destroy internal motivation.” However, several

participants see possibilities for local authorities to attract creative enterprises to deprived neighbourhoods and to better connect them with the local population. Local governments can provide cheap space and mentoring for start-ups, develop initiatives to bring entrepreneurs to local schools and establish platforms of exchange and dialogue. As local business organisations usually play an important role in the implementation of urban initiatives and programmes it is advisable they also play a role in strengthening connections between creative and high-tech enterprises and other entrepreneurs in the neighbourhood.

Overall there is consensus that the policy focus on creative and high-tech enterprises should be complemented with a multifarious strategy to connect these enterprises to the diversity of the neighbourhood. Furthermore, local governments should spend more attention to ethnic entrepreneurs working in low-end sectors like retail, pubs and restaurants. When developing urban regeneration plans for deprived neighbourhoods, local policies should pay more attention to the impact of such plans on small and migrant businesses and take measures to prevent displacement. After all, regeneration policies about not just about the physical neighbourhood but also about the residents who live there.

Statement 3: Numerous small local enterprises such as retailers, pubs and restaurants play an important role in diverse neighbourhoods by providing affordable and specialised goods and services and employment opportunities for disadvantaged people, but they often feel underappreciated by governments. Smaller enterprises feel the impact of taxation and regulation more than larger enterprises and therefore expect more from local government in terms of the provision of legal and general advice, the organisation of 'single points of contact' and the fostering of connections with them.

Integration of people with a migration background is mostly seen from the perspective of participation in the labour market. However, figures on employment rates all over Europe show very low employment rates amongst different kind of migrants. This is an indication that several thresholds occur which hinder participation in regular labour market. Some thresholds are well known: low level of qualification, discrimination, a lack of worldwide recognition of diplomas and language barriers. For some people, then, starting their own business is a negative choice due to a difficult accessibility of local labour market. For others,

however, running a small local enterprise is the most preferable option to gather an income. However, in both scenarios success is not guaranteed. We focus on the problems of these small enterprises because this kind of economic activity is overrepresented amongst ethnic groups.

Our research findings stress that several kinds of contacts or relations exist between local enterprises and government. One is taxation. This is an indirect contact, but small enterprises struggle with it. For many entrepreneurs, the primary goal is survival, therefore it is quite hard for them to respond pro-actively to market changes. Very often, these entrepreneurs have a weak position in discussions on taxation because they do not have time to organise themselves or to communicate with each other or interest groups that might defend them. Taxation might also harm ethnic diversity in the field of entrepreneurship, when it is selectively higher for small businesses, e.g. because the government wants to discourage certain economic activities (e.g. night and call shops).

Another (local or national) government instrument that small businesses are confronted with are permits and certificates. In some cities, there are too many permits to obtain, which requires contacts with several different institutions. In this respect, providing support for firms is important, especially for the less experienced entrepreneurs. Some participants plead for a more flexible system of regulations, for example in Budapest, the boundaries between formal and informal economic activities are quite rigid; they could be reconsidered from the perspective of the viability of small businesses in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods. In Denmark, it is rather difficult to start new a business, and due to EU- and national level regulations on market economy, it is hard to provide assistance to local enterprises.

Still, local governments do take initiatives to support local small businesses in the area. In Budapest, for example, a kind of incubation program for local enterprises is installed. It is conceived as part of a local economic program that is part of urban renewal. The benefits of local enterprises seem to be broad.

Discussions on policies towards local entrepreneurship have to take into account that people starting up a business can have different profiles. Participants from many different cities

report that several people with a migrant background become entrepreneurs because they are marginalised in the primary labour market and entrepreneurship is a “low-barrier way to get cash” for them. Sometimes people even start their own business because they feel discriminated in the primary labour market on the basis of their ethnicity or neighbourhood, not because of unemployment per se. They also highlight that small enterprises can have a role in social integration as well. Running such businesses helps the entrepreneurs to feel themselves part of the local society (especially for immigrants or other marginalised groups), since in the formal labour market, opportunities for these people are quite limited.

Statement #4: The resources and background of entrepreneurs in diverse neighbourhoods vary widely, while the support provided is too often standardised and ‘colour-blind’. There is a need for local governments to provide tailor-made advice and training programs in diverse neighbourhoods. For example, migrant entrepreneurs often experience problems accessing finance. Micro-credit and financial advice are important for them, especially in the start-up phase. Local governments can also promote and support intermediary local organisations, such as training bureaus, consultancies and business associations to strengthen migrant entrepreneurs. Also, taxation regimes do not often differentiate between large and small enterprises and thus undermine small business in urban neighbourhoods.

Migrant entrepreneurs are confronted with specific challenges and problems such as access to finance and (local) commercial expertise but there is often little targeted government and other support available to help them overcome these challenges and problems. In the neighbourhood Jane and Finch in Toronto, interviewees predominantly perceived business support provided by the City as rather ineffective. Despite its declaration to support entrepreneurship in lower-income communities, for instance by specific programmes offered by Enterprise Toronto, the local government was perceived as favouring those with money and neglecting entrepreneurship in deprived neighbourhoods. Interviewees from Toronto also mention the lack of capital as a strong impediment for entrepreneurs in deprived neighbourhoods. As one manager explained: “The main obstacle is the funding of their own business. If we are looking at what is called credit history [which is essential to receive a bank loan], it doesn’t exist for people in Jane and Finch. For the majority of

people.” Entrepreneurs in the area suggest that the local government should improve the access to capital for entrepreneurs from lower socio-economic backgrounds.

In northern Tallinn entrepreneurs felt that the current legislative and taxation framework is in certain aspects too much oriented towards facilitating the activity of larger enterprises and it is much harder for small or medium-sized enterprises to meet these requirements. For example, the social security tax that the employer has to pay is 33% regardless of the size of the enterprise, and the same applies for the turnover tax, which is 20%. As one entrepreneur suggested: “[We need more] legislative support. They should differentiate taxes for small and large enterprises. [...] In Estonia the social security tax and turnover tax are high. Turnover tax should be lower for small and medium-sized enterprises; that would be fair.” In Northern Milan as well, small entrepreneurs see the costs of bureaucracy and taxes as much too high: “Taxes are too much for a starting-up business. True, you have not to pay taxes in the first year, but then you have to repay later” (Italian baker).

Participants refer to a lack of information and trust in public institutions, banks and other formal organisations as a specific and important obstacle for migrant entrepreneurs to develop a successful business. In order to avoid dependence on public institutions or banks, migrant entrepreneurs often lend from friends and family. There are ways to counter this, for example by setting up micro-credit agencies, employing migrant employees to gain the trust of migrant entrepreneurs or replacing the filling in of administrative forms with oral interviews (and having a functionary fill in forms on the basis of that). The same problems exist for business organisations. Migrant entrepreneurs often do not know that these organisations exist and what they can do for them. A more active approach to involve migrant entrepreneurs in business associations seems necessary, which also requires them to be more sensitive towards diversity (e.g. when organising activities around festivities). Another strategy can be to ‘deformalise’ business associations so that asking advice from these associations feels more like asking advice from a friend.

Participants also suggest that policymakers and civil society organisations should develop more differentiated approaches towards migrant entrepreneurship depending on whether businesses depend on local neighbourhoods or not. They should target specifically businesses in deprived neighbourhoods who have difficulties in bringing new customer

groups. Other participants argue that group-targeted approaches may sometimes be necessary, but that there is a need, first and foremost, for better generic entrepreneurship policies. Some argue for policies that “aim to reach entrepreneurs on the basis of their location, not on the basis of their origin”. Policymakers should also become “more aware of the ‘diversity within diversity’.”

To conclude, migrant entrepreneurs and small businesses in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods are confronted with specific problems that require specific policy responses. For migrant entrepreneurs, there is a need for support in access to finance, the establishment of trust in formal organisations and supportive and accessible business associations. For small entrepreneurs, special tax regimes would make their business more viable.

Statement #5: Immigrant entrepreneurs, especially from smaller enterprises, are not used to co-operate with public institutions, are seldom aware of governmental support programmes and policies and often mistrust public authorities. Public institutions should build trust and engage with migrant entrepreneurs through supportive actions and effective communication as well as by minimising bureaucratic procedures.

Many immigrant entrepreneurs start from a disadvantaged position compared to native entrepreneurs. This can be due to an insufficient knowledge of the local language and legislation, lower levels of education and/or a lack of financial and social capital. Furthermore, because some immigrant entrepreneurs, especially those from smaller enterprises, are not well acquainted with public authorities and not used to co-operate with public institutions, there can be a lack of knowledge of governmental support programmes and a certain mistrust towards public authorities.

Several participants concur with the statement that there is a certain wariness towards public authorities, (“migrant entrepreneurs support each other, but they do not go to governmental services”); yet add that it is formulated too one-sidedly because often there is also distrust from public authorities towards migrant entrepreneurs. Furthermore, in some cities such as Leipzig the problem of establishing good connections between municipality

and entrepreneurs concerns both migrant as well as German entrepreneurs. More fundamentally, some participants raise the question whether it still makes sense to use the term 'migrant' entrepreneurs. In Rotterdam, for instance, "50% of the urban population has a foreign origin. By linking the terms 'migrant' and 'deprived' neighbourhoods, we create the impression that there is a problem in those neighbourhoods that needs to be solved".

When discussing policy strategies to build trust and engage with migrant entrepreneurs stakeholders mention that effective and transparent communication from both sides is crucial. One participant argues that city councils have to invest in strong and reliable communication channels with migrant entrepreneurs. In the past "wrong information is spread by migrant entrepreneurs through informal networks, for example they told that it is allowed to open shops on closing days. These entrepreneurs need to get correct information from the municipality."

Overall we can conclude that public institutions should invest in solid communication channels, minimise bureaucratic procedures and develop reach out initiatives, especially towards smaller immigrant entrepreneurs. These are crucial to address a lack of knowledge of governmental support programmes and a level of mistrust towards public authorities that might exist within these groups.

Statement 6: Local and central governments only seldom use diversity as an asset to foster entrepreneurship. Local governments and civil society organisations should reflect on the potential of diversity for entrepreneurship and the economic performance of the neighbourhood economy.

From an economic point of view, there is still a long way to go to integrate diversity in economic policies. Ethnic entrepreneurship is not yet an important issue for economic policies. But also the ethnic consumer is not yet seen as an economic asset. Although markets and businesses follow their own logic and dynamics – significantly influenced by the international context – cities do have a responsibility to develop and express a vision on

ethnic entrepreneurship and to support local economic innovation that mobilizes ethnic and cultural diversity as an asset.

The participants agree that local policies should not only focus on enterprises, but on the general effect of diversity on business and economic performance. It seems very difficult though to refine this challenge and to name and frame the general effect that is aimed for. A key success factor seems to be building trust between people with various backgrounds. Pro-diversity and anti-discrimination policies should be combined to produce positive effects. If the various social groups are needed for the economy, they must be treated equally (e.g. with respect to wages). The fact that this is stressed so explicitly, shows that trust and equal payment are not guaranteed. In this respect, economic policies should be complemented with social inclusion policies that eliminate prejudices and its effects on economic dynamics as well as social cohesion.

One of the strategies mentioned to stimulate local migrant businesses and their economic performance starts with the analysis of the social-demographic composition of the neighbourhood and its representation in the neighbourhood economy. The heterogeneity of entrepreneurs and enterprises in a neighbourhood is seen as important, since this diversity can attract certain types of businesses and more customers. The 'agglomeration economies' created by the concentrated co-existence of various economic activities in neighbourhoods can be a notable benefit of economic diversity. Therefore, not only the diversity of residents but also the diversity of businesses should be taken into account. In addition, economic diversity has an impact on social cohesion as well. In this respect, also gentrification – especially when it leads to certain economic activities being pushed out of the neighbourhood - is a relevant phenomenon that should be considered as part of the economic angle of diversity policies.

Statement #7: We found little evidence that diversity supports social mobility and out-of-poverty trajectories in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods. When developing anti-poverty strategies, policy-makers and civil society organisations should not focus on diversity per se, but on direct investments in the poor (e.g. education, job creation, etc.). Although valuable as a source of income and autonomy, migrant entrepreneurship will not address the newcomers' structural problems on the labour market, which requires inclusive labour market policies.

Policy-makers often defend social mix strategies in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods by referring to how more diverse social networks support the social integration of disadvantaged groups (e.g. by offering job opportunities, knowledge about the education system, etc.). However, our research has found little evidence that diversity effectively supports social mobility and out-of-poverty trajectories in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods. A policy implication one can derive from this is that policy-makers and civil society organisations, in order to tackle poverty, should pay priority to direct investments in the poor and their structural problems on the labour market. (e.g. education, job creation, etc.).

Most stakeholders agree that a one-sided policy focus on supporting migrant entrepreneurship cannot solve the structural problems that many migrants or newcomers are experiencing. Yet, they also see significant trump cards for ethnic entrepreneurs, which they should learn how to utilize: "it's hard for migrant entrepreneurs to employ other people. It is already hard enough for them to just earn money for themselves. On the other hand, diversity can be good for businesses. How can migrant businesses become successful? They have a connection with transnational and thus broader markets". Successful examples demonstrate that tapping into transnational markets can help migrant entrepreneurs to prosper: "In Antwerp, there is specialisation in the streets. The Handelstraat is very well known. People from far away come to shop there. Also in the Offerandestraat people come to shop there for clothes."

Still, recognising migrant entrepreneurship as a valuable and often necessary source of income for migrants and newcomers and highlighting the social role their businesses often play (in terms of access to information, social networks and informal mobility ladders),

should not distract from the actual reality that much migrant entrepreneurship is not a positive choice. It is born out of necessity due to discrimination on the labour market, the lack of jobs for low skilled people, the lack of recognition of degrees attained in other countries, etc. For many migrants, entrepreneurship is a survival strategy and in itself will not solve structural labour market problems. Policymakers should hence focus on fighting discrimination on the labour market, the creation of jobs for the low skilled and more flexibility in the recognition of foreign degrees.

Participants in the discussion highlight that starting a business should not be seen as an easy option, even if it proves to be easier than getting access to the labour market. Others warn that it is important that the children of migrant entrepreneurs are shown that there are alternatives to entrepreneurship. In some migrant families, entrepreneurship becomes a tradition that is transferred to the children, which – in the many cases in which these businesses are not particularly profitable – may reduce social mobility.

Overall, we can conclude that direct social investments works better to generate social mobility chances for disadvantaged groups than social mix policies and that inclusive labour market policies are at least as important than policies supporting migrant entrepreneurs.

3. Conclusions: governing urban diversity

One of the critical lessons for policy making and action on **social cohesion, neighbourhood attachment and everyday life** in diverse neighbourhoods is that a solid and dynamic knowledge base on the diversity of neighbourhood populations and their differing needs and habits is a pre-condition to govern urban diversity in a positive way. It is important to inform the interventions that are needed to create trust in diverse neighbourhoods. As far as the choice for housing location is concerned, policymakers should take into account that housing prices and location rather than cultural diversity are the main reasons why most people choose to live in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods. People may also choose to live in these kinds of neighbourhoods out of habit or because of the presence of family and friends. One reason that is highlighted as specifically relevant for policy-maker's approach of diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods is that, especially when parts of society are hostile to migration, the presence of co-ethnics in the neighbourhood provide ethnic minorities with higher levels of physical, psychological and social security. In addition, some people do not have any choice because housing market provides the lowest prices in diverse and/or deprived neighbourhoods.

One of the threats to social cohesion is the negative perception of the neighbourhood. Strategies to counter this involve influencing media coverage of the neighbourhood, inviting people with a lot of symbolic power and attracting headquarters to the neighbourhood. Neighbourhood representatives may also play a very important role. Although one should not expect that these representatives represent the whole community, they do have the power to open doors, represent people in their attempts to improve their living conditions and position in society or support residents in their collaboration with other groups and/or with policymakers. Also, in diverse neighbourhoods, more support needs to be given to places and institutions where diversity is seen as threatening, particularly in schools. There is, however, no consensus on whether one should strive for mixed populations in schools or choose for group based approaches in which teaching approaches can be adapted to specific cultural, linguistic or socio-economic groups. Overall, living in diversity is easier when there is basic and universally accessible social infrastructure present in the neighbourhood.

In case of gentrification, there may be strong concerns over the inflow of new urban middle classes. Although some neighbours value the improvement of the neighbourhood image, gentrification also invokes fears of higher housing prices, overcrowded services and the marginalisation of established lifestyles and activities. This concern is lower when access to housing for low-income groups is better protected. Policy-makers should hence not just focus on intercultural tensions or the behaviour of people in poverty, but take seriously the established resident's perceptions of the new urban middle classes.

As far as the **perception and approaches of diversity by policy-makers and civil society actors** is concerned, there are two core issues. Firstly, we look at how stakeholders think coherent and integrated diversity policies should be organised in such a way that there is a good division of roles between different layers of governments and civil society actors. Secondly, we will discuss how communication channels and mutual trust between different partners can be organised and strengthened.

Although stakeholders believe that an ideal-typical organisation of diversity policies does not exist, they place strong emphasis on the importance of engagement and steering from political actors and administration alike. Whether a city chooses to organise 'diversity' according to policy sectors or across policy sectors is less important than that main actors in local governments and administration take responsibility for the issue and engage in coordination. The active support of local government is seen as especially important in two regards: funding and the supporting of supra-local networks and resources. Firstly, as bottom-up initiatives often encounter difficulties when contacting local governments and applying for funding (or other forms of support), it is seen as crucial that local governments minimize bureaucratic fragmentation and simplify procedures when it comes to contacting local administration and applying for support. Although direct funding is seen as the most efficient form of support, the provision of attractive public space, logistical support and the availability of legal frameworks that enable the activities of local organisations, is also high on the agenda.

Secondly, because local initiatives are more successful if they combine their local base and social networks with supra-local networks and resources, public institutions can play a crucial role in enabling and supporting the exchange of experiences between local bottom-up initiatives around urban diversity. By setting up platforms for the exchange of experiences, different local actors can act more efficiently by sharing expertise, networks and resources.

When reflecting on the governance architecture of diversity policies, the strengths and weaknesses of different actors have to be taken into account. Coordination seems a logical task for governments to assume, while bottom-up initiatives are usually better in building bridges with various sections of the local community. While policymakers can learn about the positive potential of diversity from the more inclusive and pluralist approaches in bottom-up initiatives, bottom-up initiatives may learn from top-down policies about the conditions that are required to make living with diversity beneficial. It is also advisable to take into account differences between bigger, highly professionalized and smaller NGO's, which often rely on volunteering and lack elaborate administrative expertise and experience. It is advised to support the smaller ones and help them in learning from the bigger ones. Last, but not least, European institutions and umbrella organisations have an important role to play in empowering and scaling up local bottom-up diversity initiatives. By providing funding and supporting networking, the European Union can provide cities with the necessary maneuvering space, policy knowledge and networking capacity.

When working out the governance architecture, two caveats should be taken into account. First, it is important to take into consideration the specificities of the local and national context in which one is operating. The capacity of cities to deal with diversity is highly dependent, for instance, on how competences are divided between different layers of government or on how strong and diverse civil society actors are. Secondly, it is important to guard the independence of local initiatives and to prevent an 'osmosis' of civil society and (different layers of) government. While government support is often necessary for bottom-up initiatives to sustain themselves, it may also create a situation in which bottom-up initiatives can no longer talk on equal terms with government organisations. Policymakers

should be careful when imposing strict policy priorities and leave sufficient space for local actors to develop their own approach and respond to local needs.

Irrespective of how diversity policies are organised in a specific city or country, what all stakeholders see as crucial is the existence of strong communication channels enabling to build solid relationships between the diverse actors involved. As different actors have their own agenda's and approaches towards initiatives, there is a clear need to structure the dialogue between civil society organisations, government and local populations in a transparent way. City administrations have to explain their policy goals and approaches towards diversity clearly and should take an active role in establishing contact and communication channels with all actors involved. The establishment of trust between policymakers, civil society actors and the various constituencies of the local community is seen as highly important in enabling such effective communication and dialogue about diversity policies. Creating relationships of trust is possible in a variety of ways, including the identification of gatekeepers and the integration of members of various communities in the city administration.

To make sure information about the policies and interventions of urban policymakers and public institutions reaches significant part of the neighbourhood population, governmental actors should reach out and assemble information on the specific needs of the local population and to make sure that local initiatives are in tune with this. Also, it seems less important that residents know about specific policies, but are aware of the general attitude towards diversity. Negative attitudes towards diversity, also on other policy levels, have a negative impact on the capacity of policymakers to reach out to all sections of the neighbourhood population.

The third theme of this report was **social mobility, economic performance and entrepreneurship** in diverse neighbourhoods. One broadly shared observation is that many local policies have a one-sided focus on the highly skilled, creative or innovative enterprises and disregard the many 'non-innovative' immigrant enterprises, which are often struggling to make ends meet. Policy-makers are hence advised to develop policies that support all kinds of entrepreneurship in diverse neighbourhoods, perhaps with extra attention and support for those enterprises that are important sources of income for vulnerable families

and/or have an important social role in the neighbourhood. This can be done, for example, in the context of urban regeneration plans for deprived neighbourhoods, where policies should be developed to prevent the displacement of small and migrant businesses.

The support provided to small enterprises in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods too often is rather standardised and 'colour-blind', while small entrepreneurs are looking for tailor-made support, advice and training programs (e.g. micro-credit and financial advice). Small migrant entrepreneurs also lack trust in formal organisations and therefore policy-makers and business associations should pay special attention to generating trust with and creating accessibility for migrant entrepreneurs. Policy-makers can do so by investing in solid communication channels, minimise bureaucratic procedures and develop reach out initiatives. Many small entrepreneurs also call for taxation regimes that differentiate between large and small enterprises and thus make small businesses more viable.

Local governments and civil society organisations should reflect on the potential of diversity for entrepreneurship and the economic performance of the neighbourhood economy. This requires the building of trust between people with various backgrounds through pro-diversity and anti-discrimination policies. Economic policies should be complemented with social inclusion policies that eliminate prejudices. As for the impact of diversity on social mobility, little evidence was found that diversity supports social mobility and out-of-poverty trajectories in diverse and disadvantaged neighbourhoods. When developing anti-poverty strategies, direct investments in people living in poverty (e.g. education, job creation, etc.) is probably more effective than social mix policies. Although valuable as a source of income and autonomy, migrant entrepreneurship will not address the newcomers' structural problems on the labour market, which requires inclusive labour market policies.

Appendix 1: Programme Cross-evaluation Antwerp

Location: Prinsstraat 13, Antwerp (Hof van Liere)

Tuesday 20 September 2016

12.00 pm	Welcome and light lunch	A. Dürerzaal
1.00 pm	Plenary: introduction Presentation of DIVERCITIES research program and goals and agenda of stakeholder conference.	F. de Tassiszaal
2.00 pm	Plenary I Presentation: Governing diversity in everyday live	F. de Tassiszaal
2.45 pm	Coffee break	A. Dürerzaal
3.15 pm	Small group sessions I Social cohesion, neighbourhood attachment and everyday life in diverse neighbourhoods	Prentenkabinet; Elsschotzaal Greshamzaal
5.15 pm	Plenary II Presentation: Urban diversity policies	F. de Tassiszaal
7.00 pm	Walk to and through case study area	
7.30 pm	Diner	Eco-café Turnhoutsebaan 139

Wednesday 21 September 2016

8.30 am	Coffee	A. Dürerzaal
9.00 am	Small group sessions II Discourses, perceptions and approaches of diversity amongst policy-makers and civil society actors	Prentenkabinet Elsschotzaal; Greshamzaal
11.00 am	Plenary III Presentation: Governing diversity and its socio-economic impact	F.de Tassiszaal
11.45 am	Lunch	A. Dürerzaal
12.45 pm	Small group sessions III Social mobility, economic performance and entrepreneurship	Prentenkabinet
2.30 pm	Closing plenary Towards policy conclusions	F.de Tassiszaal
3.15 pm	Closing drinks	A. Dürerzaal

Appendix 2: List of participants

Cross-evaluations: List of participants (excluding DIVERCITIES researchers)

		grey = people who were on the list of guests, but could not attend for various reasons
Arjen Verweij	Rotterdam	Ministry of social affairs and Labour
Bilal Taner	Rotterdam	Executive Board, Municipality of Rotterdam
Annet van Otterloo	Rotterdam	Freehouse Association
Hakim Benichou	Antwerpen	Samenlevingsopbouw
Zineb Benzammour	Antwerpen	Movement X
Pamela Vaassen	Antwerpen	Movement X
Steve Weyten	Antwerpen	Dienst werk & Economie
Inge van Nieuwenhuyze	Antwerpen	Stad Antwerpen, dienst Armoedecel
Jakob Hjuler Tamsmark	Kopenhagen	The Partnership Unit, Municipality of Copenhagen commissioner in the Administration of International Recruitment and Integration under The Ministry of Immigration, Integration and Housing.
Claes Nilas	Kopenhagen	
Sven Buch	Kopenhagen	Himmerland Housing Association
Pille Metspalu	Tallinn	urban planner, Estonian Association of Spatial Planners
Teele Pehk	Tallinn	Telliskivi Neighbourhood Association
Kelly Grossthal	Tallinn	Estonian Human Rights Centre
Majid El Jarroudi	Paris	Agency for Entrepreneurial Diversity
Christine Huynh	Paris	Service Egalité, Intégration, Inclusion
Edith Burgeat	Paris	Direction of social cohesion, Paris Habitat
Michael Behling	Leipzig	Local Employment and development project
Stojan Gugutschkow	Leipzig	Department of migration and integration
Noriko Minkus	Leipzig	Japanese House
Lefteris Papagiannakis	Athene	Vice-mayor municipality of Athens, Migration Issues
Lauretta Macaulay	Athene	president of the United African Women Organisation
Gyorg Alfodi	Budapest	Advisor Mayor/ Rev8 Urban Renewal and development
Richard Ongjerth	Budapest	Hungarian Urban Knowledge Centre
Judit Schanz	budapest	Contemporary architecture centre
Marco Buemi	Milan	National Antidiscrimination office
Daniele Brigadoi	Milan	Chinese Studies, Universty of Insubria
Cologna	Milan	
Maria Grazia Allegra	Milan	Friends of the Trotter Park
Joanna Erbel	Warsaw	Congress of Urban Movements
Karolina Malcyk	Warsaw	Warsaw Mayor Plenipotentiary for Equal Treatment
Tomasz Pactwa	Warsaw	Office for support and Social Projects
Francesco Giuseppe Genova	Zurich	Foreign Council/ ENAIP Switzerland

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